

SERVICE QUALITY AND INTERNAL AND EXTERNAL STAKEHOLDERS' SATISFACTION IN THE CITY SCHOOLS DIVISION OF CABUYAO

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ABSTRACT

Service Quality and stakeholders' satisfaction are two significant elements in organizational management and sustainability. The operational conditions, as well as the high level of competition, are forces that require the company to strictly adhere to excellent services. Stakeholders' satisfaction is a modern approach to quality in businesses and organizations and it contributes to the formation of truly client-focused organizations and cultures. Measuring stakeholders' satisfaction provides fast, relevant, and objective input on the preferences and expectations of stakeholders. In this manner, a company's performance may be evaluated for a set of satisfaction dimensions that show a corporate organization's strong and weak aspects. A better organization with standard quality service and objectives that enable enhanced employee competencies emerges from increasing stakeholders' satisfaction. The research determined the relationship between the level of service quality and the level of internal and external stakeholders' satisfaction in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao and discussed the issues and concerns, as well as the difficulties encountered, that could potentially impede meeting the goal of stakeholders' satisfaction and retention. A total of 470 surveys were collected at random using an adopted instrument and the model was analyzed and evaluated using the Mean, Four-point Likert Scale, T-test and Pearson Product-moment Correlation. The analysis revealed the existence of a small but significant positive relationship between the level of service quality and stakeholders' satisfaction. Furthermore, the study proposed an action plan to develop and improve additional techniques to reinforce the ongoing service quality and increase the productivity and confidence of SDO employees.

Keywords: *Service Quality, Stakeholders' Satisfaction*

INTRODUCTION

Due to global economic shifts, a variety of service industries have changed the way they conduct business in an effort to draw and retain clients. In today's highly competitive business landscape, organizations are constantly seeking ways to gain a competitive edge, drive growth, and deliver exceptional value to their customers. One crucial avenue for achieving these objectives lies in the effective utilization of comprehensive services. As it is, services play a pivotal role in supporting businesses across various sectors, enabling them to optimize their operations, enhance customer experiences, and unlock new opportunities for success. By examining the wide range of services available, their benefits, and their influence on different aspects of organizational functioning, aiming to shed light on the critical role that services play in enhancing overall business performance.

In the study of Willot (2020), fifty-two percent (52%) of customers continuously patronized products and services from a company for they were experiencing high service quality. These figures suggested that a lot of elements, including customer satisfaction and service quality, were crucial for a business to be profitable. However, finding ways to obtain and keep such variables was still, and had always been, a crucial problem.

One of the significant challenges encountered in maintaining service quality here in the Philippines is consistently delivering a high standard of service across various customer interactions and touchpoints. One of the main factors in a customer's decision to come back is frequently the perception of quality service. Building a stronger relationship is the first step in providing better service.

In recent decades, both the public and private sectors in the Philippines demonstrate a strong commitment to achieving the highest levels of customer satisfaction. The main factors identifying customer satisfaction include safety, technical and efficiency, personal attention, and personnel providing a sense of comfort. Customers' needs are evolving quickly, and this shows that businesses need to be proactive in meeting those needs. One of the significant challenges encountered in achieving customer satisfaction is meeting ever-increasing customer expectations. In today's highly connected and competitive world, customers become more discerning and demanding. They expect personalized experiences, prompt responses, and seamless interactions across various touchpoints.

Service quality is a critical factor in customer satisfaction and loyalty, and businesses face several challenges in ensuring a consistent and exceptional service experience. Based on the study conducted by Suciptawati et al. (2019), customer satisfaction and service quality were seen as essential elements in any organization since they had a direct impact on how well a business retains its customers. Indeed, customer happiness was believed to come through providing high-quality services.

Studies are developed to determine the pre-existence of internal and external stakeholders' satisfaction and considering that internal and external stakeholders' satisfaction varies based on many other factors. The one who set up higher level service quality retains higher level client satisfaction and can achieve a sustainable global competitive advantage. By investigating the complex dynamics between service quality and customer satisfaction, this research contributed to the existing body of knowledge in the service industry. The findings and recommendations derived from this research assisted City Schools Division of Cabuyao in designing and implementing effective strategies to optimize service quality, meet customer expectations, and ultimately achieve higher levels of customer satisfaction.

For the past years, service quality provided in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao has received little attention. This meant that deliberate efforts and standard operating procedures were supposed to be utilized to direct the delivery of services or to control the quality of its service to gain client satisfaction. Unread comments and unsolicited feedback have occasionally made it difficult to respond right away. Therefore, the study has contributed to gathering a large amount of feedback from the stakeholders receiving the service. Client satisfaction has been an area of concern in any government agency that built trust, achieve competitive advantage and sustainable growth through service quality. The neglect of service quality has led to unwanted feedback, negative image and reputation, loss of trust from public and stakeholders.

Finally, this study determined the critical dimensions of service quality and their association to internal and external stakeholders' satisfaction. By conducting a comprehensive analysis of the existing literature, this study provided valuable insights for organization seeking to enhance the service offerings and improve overall client satisfaction. The researcher was highly motivated to identify the relationship between service quality and internal and external stakeholders' satisfaction in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao.

Research Questions

The main idea of the study was to determine and gain an understanding of the service quality and internal and external stakeholders' satisfaction in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao. To develop a program, the Division Office identified the significant difference and relationship between service quality and internal and external stakeholders' satisfaction. Specifically, this study answered the following questions:

1. What is the level of service quality in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao as assessed by internal and external stakeholders in terms of:

- 1.1 Reliability,
- 1.2. Responsiveness,
- 1.3. Empathy,
- 1.4. Assurance, and
- 1.5. Tangibility?

2. What is the level of satisfaction among internal and external stakeholders in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao in terms of:

- 2.1 Responsiveness,
- 2.2. Reliability,
- 2.3. Access and Facilities,
- 2.4. Communication,
- 2.5. Cost,
- 2.6. Integrity, and
- 2.7. Assurance?

3. Is there any significant difference between the assessment of the internal and external stakeholders on the level of service quality and level of satisfaction in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao?

4. Is there any significant relationship between the level of service quality and level of satisfaction among the internal and external stakeholders in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao?

5. Based on the findings of the study, what program may be proposed?

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a quantitative research design. The descriptive-correlational method of research describes the current state of a variable and is used to evaluate the extent of a relationship between the variables using statistical data. This study also utilized two questionnaires namely: Service Quality, and Internal and External Stakeholders' Satisfaction Assessment Tool to collect the data which were gathered from 235 teaching/non-teaching personnel (internal stakeholders) and 235 parents of the students (external stakeholders) in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao. The study used a G power program to identify the number of respondents with an effect size of .15, a margin of error of .05, and a confidence level of .95

RESULTS

Table 1.1

Level of Service Quality in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao as Assessed by Internal and External Stakeholders in terms of Reliability

Indicators in terms of Reliability	Internal		External		Composite		Rank
	$\bar{X}$	VI	$\bar{X}$	VI	$\bar{X}$	VI	
1. SDO Cabuyao personnel provide service as promised.	3.52	VG	3.55	VG	3.54	VG	1
2. SDO Cabuyao personnel are dependable in handling clients' service problems.	3.41	VG	3.44	VG	3.43	VG	3
3. SDO Cabuyao personnel perform services right the first time.	3.38	VG	3.38	VG	3.38	VG	4.5
4. SDO Cabuyao personnel inspire trust and confidence in clients.	3.42	VG	3.34	VG	3.38	VG	4.5
5. SDO Cabuyao personnel have speed and ease of procedures.	3.49	VG	3.45	VG	3.47	VG	2
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.44	VG	3.43	VG	3.44	VG	

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/ Very Good 1.75 – 2.49 Disagree (D)/Fair
 2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A)/ Good 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/ Poor

Table 1.2

Level of Service Quality in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao as Assessed by Internal and External Stakeholders in terms of Responsiveness

Indicators in terms of Responsiveness	Internal		External		Composite		Rank
	$\bar{X}$	VI	$\bar{X}$	VI	$\bar{X}$	VI	
1. SDO Cabuyao personnel are prompt in service to clients.	3.44	VG	3.40	VG	3.42	VG	4.5
2. SDO Cabuyao personnel are sympathetic and reassuring.	3.46	VG	3.38	VG	3.42	VG	4.5
3. SDO Cabuyao personnel are always ready for needed documents.	3.38	VG	3.49	VG	3.44	VG	3
4. SDO Cabuyao personnel are responsive to the needs of clients.	3.42	VG	3.49	VG	3.46	VG	1.5
5. SDO Cabuyao personnel are friendly and courteous.	3.45	VG	3.47	VG	3.46	VG	1.5
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.43	VG	3.45	VG	3.44	VG	

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/ Very Good 1.75 – 2.49 Disagree (D)/Fair
 2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A)/ Good 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/ Poor

Table 1.3

Level of Service Quality in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao as Assessed by Internal and External Stakeholders in terms of Empathy

Indicators in terms of Empathy	Internal		External		Composite		Rank
	$\bar{X}$	VI	$\bar{X}$	VI	$\bar{X}$	VI	
1. SDO Cabuyao personnel are giving clients individual attention.	3.46	VG	3.33	VG	3.40	VG	2
2. SDO Cabuyao personnel are never too busy to respond to requests.	3.41	VG	3.31	VG	3.36	VG	3
3. SDO Cabuyao personnel have the best interest at heart.	3.40	VG	3.28	VG	3.34	VG	4
4. SDO Cabuyao personnel understand your specific needs.	3.40	VG	3.24	VG	3.32	VG	5
5. SDO Cabuyao personnel are approachable and readily available.	3.48	VG	3.40	VG	3.44	VG	1
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.43	VG	3.31	VG	3.37	VG	
Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/ Very Good		1.75 – 2.49 Disagree (D)/Fair					
2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A)/ Good		1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/ Poor					

Table 1.4

Level of Service Quality in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao as Assessed by Internal and External Stakeholders in terms of Assurance

Indicators in terms of Assurance	Internal		External		Composite		Rank
	$\bar{X}$	VI	$\bar{X}$	VI	$\bar{X}$	VI	
1. SDO Cabuyao personnel maintain clients' confidentiality.	3.46	VG	3.38	VG	3.42	VG	1.5
2. SDO Cabuyao personnel are well-versed in procedure explanation.	3.43	VG	3.40	VG	3.42	VG	1.5
3. SDO Cabuyao personnel can meet the allotted response time.	3.40	VG	3.36	VG	3.38	VG	3
4. SDO Cabuyao personnel provide high-quality information.	3.40	VG	3.26	VG	3.33	VG	4
5. SDO Cabuyao personnel can answer question with confidence.	3.39	VG	3.31	VG	3.35	VG	5
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.42	VG	3.34	VG	3.38	VG	
Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/ Very Good		1.75 – 2.49 Disagree (D)/Fair					
2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A)/ Good		1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/ Poor					

Table 1.5

Level of Service Quality in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao as Assessed by Internal and External Stakeholders in terms of Tangibility

Indicators in terms of Tangibility	Internal		External		Composite		Rank
	$\bar{X}$	VI	$\bar{X}$	VI	$\bar{X}$	VI	
1. SDO Cabuyao has an accessible service place.	3.33	VG	3.23	VG	3.28	VG	5
2. SDO Cabuyao has displayed signages.	3.37	VG	3.29	VG	3.33	VG	3
3. SDO Cabuyao has a spacious waiting area.	3.38	VG	3.40	VG	3.39	VG	2
4. SDO Cabuyao has enough light and air circulation.	3.34	VG	3.26	VG	3.30	VG	4
5. SDO Cabuyao provides tables and chairs.	3.43	VG	3.43	VG	3.43	VG	1
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.37	VG	3.32	VG	3.35	VG	

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/ Very Good
 2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A)/ Good
 1.75 – 2.49 Disagree (D)/Fair
 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/ Poor

Table 2.1

Level of Satisfaction among Internal and External Stakeholders in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao in terms of Responsiveness

Indicators in terms of Responsiveness	Internal		External		Composite		Rank
	$\bar{X}$	VI	$\bar{X}$	VI	$\bar{X}$	VI	
1. SDO Cabuyao personnel are willing to help and assist.	3.52	FS	3.45	FS	3.49	FS	1
2. SDO Cabuyao personnel respond promptly to your needs and requests.	3.42	FS	3.42	FS	3.42	FS	5
3. SDO Cabuyao personnel show the frequency of the service.	3.52	FS	3.43	FS	3.48	FS	2
4. SDO Cabuyao personnel show professionalism.	3.43	FS	3.44	FS	3.44	FS	3.5
5. SDO Cabuyao personnel are swift in delivering the result.	3.45	FS	3.43	FS	3.44	FS	3.5
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.47	FS	3.43	FS	3.45	FS	

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree(SA)/Fully Satisfied
 2.50 – 3.24 Agree(A)/Satisfied
 1.75 – 2.49 Disagree (D)/Partially Satisfied
 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree(SD)/Not Satisfied

Table 2.2

Level of Satisfaction among Internal and External Stakeholders in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao in terms of Reliability

Indicators in terms of Reliability	Internal		External		Composite		Rank
	$\bar{X}$	VI	$\bar{X}$	VI	$\bar{X}$	VI	
1. SDO Cabuyao personnel provide what was needed and what was promised, in accordance with the policy and standards, with zero to a minimal error rate.	3.42	FS	3.41	FS	3.42	FS	1
2. SDO Cabuyao personnel provide promises to do something by a certain time.	3.37	FS	3.38	FS	3.38	FS	4.5
3. SDO Cabuyao personnel show a sincere interest in solving problems.	3.37	FS	3.40	FS	3.39	FS	3
4. SDO Cabuyao personnel make information easily obtainable by the clients.	3.37	FS	3.39	FS	3.38	FS	4.5
5. SDO Cabuyao personnel provide accurate information and services.	3.40	FS	3.41	FS	3.41	FS	2
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.38	FS	3.40	FS	3.39	FS	
Legend:	3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/Fully Satisfied 2.50 – 3.24 Agree(A)/Satisfied			1.75 – 2.49 Disagree (D)/Partially Satisfied 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/Not Satisfied			

Table 2.3

Level of Satisfaction among Internal and External Stakeholders in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao in terms of Access and Facilities

Indicators in terms of Access and Facilities	Internal		External		Composite		Rank
	$\bar{X}$	VI	$\bar{X}$	VI	$\bar{X}$	VI	
1. SDO Cabuyao has a convenient location, ample amenities for a comfortable transaction, clear signages, and modes of technology	3.30	FS	3.26	FS	3.28	FS	5
2. SDO Cabuyao has modern equipment.	3.32	FS	3.29	FS	3.31	FS	3.5
3. SDO Cabuyao has shelves, customer service counters, computers, and lights that are visually appealing.	3.32	FS	3.30	FS	3.31	FS	3.5
4. SDO Cabuyao provides drinking water and restrooms.	3.35	FS	3.36	FS	3.36	FS	2
5. SDO Cabuyao holds professional appearance.	3.39	FS	3.41	FS	3.40	FS	1
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.34	FS	3.33	FS	3.34	FS	
Legend:	3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/Fully Satisfied 2.50 – 3.24 Agree(A)/Satisfied			1.75 – 2.49 Disagree (D)/Partially Satisfied 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/Not Satisfied			

Table 2.4

Level of Satisfaction among Internal and External Stakeholders in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao in terms of Communication

Indicators in terms of Communication	Internal		External		Composite		Rank
	$\bar{X}$	VI	$\bar{X}$	VI	$\bar{X}$	VI	
1. SDO Cabuyao personnel act keeping citizens and businesses informed in a language they can easily understand, as well as listening to their feedback.	3.49	FS	3.50	FS	3.50	FS	1
2. Client received clarity and accuracy of information.	3.43	FS	3.46	FS	3.45	FS	4
3. SDO Cabuyao personnel effectively convey the intended message during the communication process.	3.47	FS	3.48	FS	3.48	FS	2
4. SDO Cabuyao personnel actively listen to your needs and concerns.	3.42	FS	3.44	FS	3.43	FS	5
5. SDO Cabuyao personnel has knowledge of the subject matter being discussed.	3.46	FS	3.46	FS	3.46	FS	3
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.45	FS	3.47	FS	3.46	FS	
Legend:	3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/Fully Satisfied 2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A)/Satisfied			1.75 – 2.49 Disagree (D)/Partially Satisfied 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/Not Satisfied			

Table 2.5

Level of Satisfaction among Internal and External Stakeholders in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao in terms of Cost

Indicators in terms of Cost	Internal		External		Composite		Rank
	$\bar{X}$	VI	$\bar{X}$	VI	$\bar{X}$	VI	
1. Satisfaction with the timeliness of the billing, billing process/es, preferred methods of payment period, value for money, acceptable range of costs, and qualitative information on the cost of each service.	3.53	FS	3.42	FS	3.48	FS	1
2. Cost of the service align with your expectations and the level of quality you received.	3.43	FS	3.39	FS	3.41	FS	4
3. SDO Cabuyao provide with clear and transparent pricing information before utilizing the service.	3.49	FS	3.37	FS	3.43	FS	2
4. SDO Cabuyao provide you with an itemized breakdown of the costs involved, such as service fees, additional charges, or taxes.	3.46	FS	3.38	FS	3.42	FS	3
5. Cost of the service accurately reflects the level of professionalism, expertise, and attention to detail exhibited.	3.43	FS	3.33	FS	3.38	FS	5
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.47	FS	3.38	FS	3.43	FS	
Legend:	3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/Fully Satisfied 2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A)/Satisfied			1.75 – 2.49 Disagree (D)/Partially Satisfied 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/Not Satisfied			

Table 2.6

Level of Satisfaction among Internal and External Stakeholders in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao in terms of Integrity

Indicators in terms of Integrity	Internal		External		Composite		Rank
	$\bar{X}$	VI	$\bar{X}$	VI	$\bar{X}$	VI	
1. SDO Cabuyao personnel has the capability to perform their duties, product, and service knowledge, understand client needs, helpfulness, and good work relationships.	3.50	FS	3.44	FS	3.47	FS	1
2. SDO Cabuyao personnel are polite and respectful in conversation.	3.43	FS	3.45	FS	3.44	FS	4
3. SDO Cabuyao personnel are friendly.	3.43	FS	3.47	FS	3.45	FS	3
4. SDO Cabuyao personnel are caring and concerned to clients.	3.43	FS	3.48	FS	3.46	FS	2
5. Clients feel safe in their transactions with personnel at the counters.	3.39	FS	3.41	FS	3.40	FS	5
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.43	FS	3.45	FS	3.44	FS	
Legend:	3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/Fully Satisfied 2.50 – 3.24 Agree(A)/Satisfied			1.75 – 2.49 Disagree (D)/Partially Satisfied 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/Not Satisfied			

Table 2.7

Level of Satisfaction among Internal and External Stakeholders in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao in terms of Assurance

Indicators in terms of Integrity	Internal		External		Composite		Rank
	$\bar{X}$	VI	$\bar{X}$	VI	$\bar{X}$	VI	
1. SDO Cabuyao personnel are honest, fair, and trustworthy in each service while dealing with clients and businesses.	3.45	FS	3.49	FS	3.47	FS	3
2. SDO Cabuyao keep records with confidentiality and accuracy.	3.46	FS	3.44	FS	3.45	FS	5
3. SDO Cabuyao personnel are knowledgeable of the service offered.	3.46	FS	3.51	FS	3.49	FS	1.5
4. Clients have confidence and trust in personnel in service.	3.43	FS	3.48	FS	3.46	FS	4
5. Clients have a safe transaction with personnel.	3.46	FS	3.52	FS	3.49	FS	1.5
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.45	FS	3.49	FS	3.47	FS	
Legend:	3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/Fully Satisfied 2.50 – 3.24 Agree(A)/Satisfied			1.75 – 2.49 Disagree (D)/Partially Satisfied 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/Not Satisfied			

Table 3.1

Test of Significant Difference on the Assessment of the Internal and External Stakeholders on the Level of Service Quality in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao

Sub-variables		Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F Ratio	Sig.	Remarks	Decision
Reliability	Between Groups	.019	1					
	Within Groups	136.787	468	.019	.066	.798	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
	Total	136.806	469	.292				
Responsiveness	Between Groups	.038	1					
	Within Groups	127.138	468	.038	.138	.710	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
	Total	127.175	469	.272				
Empathy	Between Groups	1.621	1					
	Within Groups	146.191	468	1.621	5.189	.023	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Total	147.811	469	.312				
Assurance	Between Groups	.629	1					
	Within Groups	135.734	468	.629	2.170	.141	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
	Total	136.364	469	.290				
Tangibility	Between Groups	.286	1					
	Within Groups	135.083	468	.286	.992	.320	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
	Total	135.369	469	.289				

Level of significance 0.05

Table 3.2

Test of Significant Difference on the Assessment of the Internal and External Stakeholders on the Level of Satisfaction in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao

Sub-variables		Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F Ratio	Sig.	Remarks	Decision
Responsiveness	Between Groups	.123	1					
	Within Groups	138.252	468	.123	.416	.519	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
	Total	138.374	469	.295				
Reliability	Between Groups	.014	1					
	Within Groups	135.101	468	.014	.050	.823	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
	Total	135.115	469	.289				
Access and Facilities	Between groups	.017	1					
	Within Groups	160.230	468	.017	.049	.825	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
	Total	160.246	469	.342				
Communication	Between Groups	.017	1					
	Within Groups	132.107	468	.017	.059	.808	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
	Total	132.124	469	.282				
Cost	Between Groups	.974	1					
	Within Groups	150.149	468	.974	3.037	.082	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
	Total	151.123	469	.321				
Integrity	Between Groups	.022	1					
	Within Groups	155.721	468	.022	.065	.798	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
	Total	155.743	469	.333				
Assurance	Between Groups	.157	1					
	Within Groups	153.061	468	.157	.481	.488	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
	Total	153.219	469	.327				

Level of significance 0.05

Table 4

Test of Significant Relationship between the Level of Service Quality and Level of Satisfaction among the Internal and External Stakeholders in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao

Service Quality	Satisfaction	r value	P value	Remarks	Decision
Reliability	Responsiveness	.409**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Reliability	.422**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Access and Facilities	.386**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Communication	.400**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Cost	.385**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
Responsiveness	Integrity	.390**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Assurance	.407**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Responsiveness	.422**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Reliability	.448**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Access and Facilities	.402**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
Empathy	Communication	.424**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Cost	.387**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Integrity	.411**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Assurance	.418**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Responsiveness	.372**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
Assurance	Reliability	.371**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Access and Facilities	.347**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Communication	.336**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Cost	.348**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Integrity	.341**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
Tangibility	Assurance	.342**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Responsiveness	.392**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Reliability	.395**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Access and Facilities	.361**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Communication	.380**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
Assurance	Cost	.368**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Integrity	.380**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Assurance	.366**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Responsiveness	.338**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Reliability	.341**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
Tangibility	Access and Facilities	.350**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Communication	.327**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Cost	.325**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Integrity	.336**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Assurance	.298**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀

**Correlational at the level 0.01

*Correlational at the level 0.05(Two-tailed)

Table 5

Proposed Action Plan to Enhance the Service Quality in terms of Empathy in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao

<i>Project CARE: Cultivating Authentic Relationship with Empathy</i>					
KEY AREAS	OBJECTIVES	STRATEGIES/ ACTIVITIES	FREQUENCY	PERSONS INVOLVED	SUCCESS INDICATORS
Cultivating Leadership and Culture	To elevate leadership commitment and foster a culture of empathy	Leadership Modeling Recognition Empathetic Leadership	for Annually Quarterly	City Schools Division of Cabuyao Personnel	85-90% of employees elevate leadership commitment and foster a culture of empathy
Amplify Employee Training	To promote ongoing training and focus on active listening, understanding, and stakeholders' perspectives	Empathy Workshops Peer-to-Peer Learning	Annually	City Schools Division of Cabuyao Personnel	90-95% of employees promote ongoing training and focus on active listening, understanding, and stakeholders' perspectives
Refine Communication Skills	To improve communication skills, emphasize clear and positive communication and enhance both verbal and written interactions	Body Language Awareness Communication Style Assessments	Annually	City Schools Division of Cabuyao Personnel	85-90% of employees improve communication skills, emphasize clear and positive communication, and enhance both verbal and written interactions
Establish Stakeholders' Feedback Mechanism	To implement a systematic process for collecting stakeholders feedback to understand satisfaction levels	Real-time Feedback Tools Employee Training on Handling Feedback	Annually	City Schools Division of Cabuyao Personnel	90-95% of employees implement a systematic process for collecting stakeholders feedback to understand satisfaction levels

DISCUSSION

Table 1.1

Reliability was **Very Good (3.44)** in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao as assessed by Internal and External Stakeholders. All indicators were verbally interpreted as Very Good. Furthermore, the indicator “SDO Cabuyao personnel provide service as promised” had the highest computed mean of **3.54**. Meanwhile, the indicators “SDO Cabuyao personnel perform services right the first time” and “SDO Cabuyao personnel inspire trust and confidence in clients” had the lowest computed mean of **3.38**. It can be concluded that internal and external Stakeholders in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao are very satisfied in terms of Reliability. SDO Cabuyao personnel delivering services as promised. It makes sure that they are quick and simple to deal with while managing customer service issues. However, to enable employees to work toward certain objectives and targets connected to their commitment, they should concentrate more on delivering services correctly for the first time to inspire clients' confidence and faith. Identifying the actions that deserve praise and recognition is helpful.

To support the result, Varsanis et al. (2019) mentioned that service quality provision was one of the most important aspects of hotel businesses' attempts to fortify their position in the fiercely competitive environment and pursue sustainability, profitability, and growth prospects. A quality managerial staff with knowledge, skills, professionalism, interpersonal skills, conscientiousness, a high sense of responsibility, and consistency in the company's effort to continually improved the quality was found to be necessary for immediate and effective problem solving, quick and error-free or omitted service, quick and accurate information, compliance with the agreed upon, and the provision of personal and individualized care. Furthermore, Sherman (2019, as cited in Vu, 2021) studied the service quality importance did not just result through customer loss but had a significant positive impact when doing it correctly, such as operating costs reduction, lowering purchasing barriers and increasing sales. It required more time and money to attract new customers as opposed to retaining established ones.

Table 1.2

Responsiveness was **Very Good (3.44)** in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao as assessed by Internal and External Stakeholders. All indicators were verbally interpreted as Very Good. Furthermore, the indicators “SDO Cabuyao personnel are responsive to the needs of clients” and “SDO Cabuyao personnel are friendly and courteous” had the highest computed mean of **3.46**. Meanwhile, the indicators “SDO Cabuyao personnel are prompt in service to clients” and “SDO Cabuyao personnel are sympathetic and reassuring” had the lowest computed mean of **3.42**.

It is concluded that both Internal and External Stakeholders in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao are very satisfied with Responsiveness because they think SDO personnel were being kind and comforting, alertness is there that meet the needs of clients, provides consistent quality of service. SDO Cabuyao personnel has to make sure

they meet the customer perception and expectation, should be constantly prepared with the necessary documents needed by the clients to prevent future problems. Having said that, SDO personnel gives attention on providing timely service and someone who can really understand any situations, showing sympathy and a public servant who understand clients' feelings.

It is consistent with the findings of Dewi (2019) that excellent service quality was based not only on the service provider's perspective but also on service users' perceptions. The service user perception of service quality was a comprehensive assessment of a service. Customer's need was the key to service quality and a significant factor in business strategy. Factors influenced service users' perception included service encounters, evidence of service, company image, and service price. Quality of service that can satisfy customers is proven to increase profitability to be a competitive advantage tool. Excellent service quality created repeat purchases, positive word of mouth, customer loyalty, and competitive service differentiation. In addition, Fitzsimmons et al. (2018, as cited in Ting et al., 2019) stated that service quality refers to the overall excellence or superiority of the services provided by an organization. It was a measure of how well a service meets or exceeds customer expectations and requirements.

Table 1.3

Empathy was Very Good (3.37) in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao as assessed by Internal and External Stakeholders. All indicators were verbally interpreted as Very Good. Furthermore, the indicator "SDO Cabuyao personnel are approachable and readily available" had the highest computed mean of **3.44**. Meanwhile, the indicator "SDO Cabuyao personnel understand your specific needs" had the lowest computed mean of **3.32**.

The results infer that both internal and external stakeholders in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao are very satisfied in terms of Empathy. Clients have assessed SDO Cabuyao personnel as being accessible, friendly and each client has been given attention. Despite SDO Cabuyao personnel having lots of paperwork and workloads, they are never too busy to answer inquiries as part of value-added service quality and recognizing individual expectations.

Evidently, the study conducted by Sameena (2020) stated that two aspects of service quality, namely core and value-added service quality, have been the focus of attention in educational institutions. The fundamental service quality metrics created by the industry pioneer made up the core service quality. These were reliability, responsiveness, empathy, assurance, and tangibles. With every customer, or even just one customer all the time, service quality varies. As a result, marketing jobs are difficult. They must make sure that these aspects of the education services are used more effectively to satisfy the various needs of the clients. Moreover, Jones et al. (2019) stated that effective communication skills, including active listening and empathy, are essential for building rapport and understanding customer needs. Service providers who actively

listen, validate customer concerns and communicate understanding demonstrate empathy, contributing to enhanced service quality perceptions.

Table 1.4

Assurance was **Very Good (3.38)** in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao as assessed by Internal and External Stakeholders. All indicators were verbally interpreted as Very Good. Furthermore, the indicators “SDO Cabuyao personnel maintain clients’ confidentiality” and “SDO Cabuyao personnel are well-versed in procedure explanation” had the highest computed mean of **3.42**. Meanwhile, the indicator “SDO Cabuyao personnel can answer question with confidence” had the lowest computed mean of **3.35**.

It can be concluded that both internal and external stakeholders are very satisfied in terms of Assurance in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao. Client’s confidentiality is genuinely maintained by all departments in SDO Cabuyao as well the personnel are knowledgeable about explaining procedures to clear things to avoid confusion for both sides. SDO Cabuyao personnel ensures that they can be able to respond within the designated time and make necessary adjustments if needed in every transaction. Clients are more particular in delivering excellent information and must pay attention to prevent complaints and could correct existing conflicts or problems.

In like manner, Choi et al. (2022) mentioned that explicit service guarantees and policies provide customers with assurance regarding the quality and reliability of the service. Offering warranties, satisfaction guarantees, and refund policies communicates confidence in the service offering and mitigates perceived risks. Likewise, according to Valenzo et al. (2019), evaluating the quality of public transport service is an area of opportunity that should not be missed, as it is beneficial for meeting the necessities of society and allowing organizations to improve their activities. This gave them the opportunity to correct the problems presented in the service, to become a profitable business, without neglecting the users of this service.

Table 1.5

Tangibility was **Very Good (3.35)** in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao as assessed by Internal and External Stakeholders. All indicators were verbally interpreted as Very Good. Furthermore, the indicator “SDO Cabuyao provides tables and chairs” had the highest computed mean of **3.43**. Meanwhile, the indicator “SDO Cabuyao has an accessible service place” had the lowest computed mean of **3.28**.

It can be concluded that both internal and external Stakeholders in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao are very satisfied in terms of Tangibility. It is proven that SDO Cabuyao provides tables and chairs that can accommodate large number of clients visiting the offices with a spacious waiting area and has displayed signages allocating different offices. These are some of the features that can enhance customer services to meet the expectations and satisfaction of the clients.

Certainly, Johnson and Patel (2019) mentioned that well-designed and maintained physical facilities contribute to positive perceptions of service quality. Cleanliness, aesthetics, and comfort of facilities influence customer experiences and shape their overall satisfaction levels. Likewise, Fida et al. (2020, as cited in Dider, 2021) defined service quality as the fundamental abilities of a specific business or sector to satisfy the intended client expectations. Moreover, Zygiaris et al. (2022) mentioned that service quality can be considered crucial because it helped to increase an organization's competitiveness. Organizations specifically used this information about consumer perceptions of service quality as a tool to enhance their customer services. For instance, understanding the necessary customer service would make it easier to facilitate training programs aimed at educating all employees on how to enhance and provide high-quality client services. Besides, information about client services would be crucial in the firm's decision-making process regarding its marketing initiatives, giving it a competitive advantage in the market.

Table 2.1

Responsiveness was Fully Satisfied (3.45) in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao as assessed by the internal and external stakeholders. All indicators were verbally interpreted as Fully Satisfied. Furthermore, the indicator "SDO Cabuyao personnel are willing to help and assist" had the highest computed mean of **3.49**. Meanwhile, the indicator "SDO Cabuyao personnel respond promptly to your needs and requests" had the lowest computed mean of **3.42**.

It can be concluded that both internal and external stakeholders in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao are highly satisfied in terms of Responsiveness because SDO Cabuyao personnel are eager to lend a hand. It is the act of offering assistance and support to both new and current clients. It is a crucial component of the whole client experience. Employees at SDO Cabuyao are required to report on how frequently they meet customer requests and gauge their general level of satisfaction using the feedback facility on a weekly basis. Everyone also exhibits professionalism in any circumstance including a variety of client personalities and behaviors. SDO Cabuyao personnel ensures immediate response in delivering the result to surpass client expectations. Clients, however, expect a quicker response to their demands and inquiries.

Kotler (2019) provided evidence to support the findings stating that customer satisfaction was a feeling of happiness or dissatisfaction that someone experienced after comparing a product's performance to what was anticipated. Customer satisfaction was measured by whether performance meets or exceeds expectations. If performance falls short of expectations, there were unhappy customers; if performance surpasses expectations, there were satisfied consumers. Correspondingly, according to Muralidharan et al. (2023), customers were deemed to be individuals who were satisfied with any company unit, which incorporated into its master plan. The immediate calculation of the reward and client satisfaction were essential success measures. With a better grasp of consumer perception, businesses identified what efforts must be made to suit

the demands of their customers. It assisted in recognizing the company's own strengths and shortcomings, as well as mapping the route for future upgrades and advances.

Table 2.2

Reliability was **Fully Satisfied (3.39)** in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao as assessed by the internal and external stakeholders. All indicators were verbally interpreted as Fully Satisfied. Furthermore, the indicator “SDO Cabuyao personnel provide what was needed and what was promised, in accordance with the policy and standards, with zero to a minimal error rate” had the highest computed mean of **3.42**. Meanwhile, the indicators “SDO Cabuyao personnel provide promises to do something by a certain time” and SDO Cabuyao personnel make information easily obtainable by the clients” had the lowest computed mean of **3.38**.

It is concluded that the majority of SDO Cabuyao personnel fulfill their commitments and deliver on their promises in compliance with the policy and standards, with very little to no error rate which is why both internal and external stakeholders in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao are highly satisfied in terms of Reliability. SDO Cabuyao personnel deliver accurate information and services through client participation, and this kind of engagement not only improves the service but also raises customer satisfaction. When clients visit the office, they are eager to provide feedback and show willingness to spread the positive word-of-mouth because they perceive that SDO Cabuyao personnel genuinely cares about finding solutions to issues that are highly appreciated.

In supporting the findings, it is worth mentioning the research study by Wu et al. (2020), which confirmed that customer satisfaction lies on the traditional model of service, reflected a one-way distribution wherein customers get the service exactly how the provider distributed it to them. Yet, when the customer's willingness to assist in service building rises, customer participation quickly emerged throughout service delivery. The method of service delivery in the financial services sector has evolved and changed considerably over time. Service delivery had changed from being one-way to including clients in the process by expressing their wants. Such involvement not only enhanced the service but also increased consumers' satisfaction. This study evaluated whether customer participation increased customer satisfaction by examining the factors that influenced it, such as interactional fairness, customer education, affective commitment, and firm support. Markedly, Wirtz et al. (2012, as cited in Abidin, 2023) stated that customers who were satisfied and happy with the products or services provided tend to repurchase, spread positive word-of-mouth, and even become ambassadors for a company. Conversely, dissatisfied customers seek and switch to other products or service providers.

Table 2.3

Access and Facilities were **Fully Satisfied (3.34)** in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao as assessed by the internal and external stakeholders. All indicators were verbally interpreted as Fully Satisfied. Furthermore, the indicator “SDO Cabuyao holds

professional appearance” had the highest computed mean of **3.40**. Meanwhile, the indicator “SDO Cabuyao has a convenient location, ample amenities for a comfortable transaction, clear signages, and modes of technology” had the lowest computed mean of **3.28**.

It can be concluded that both internal and external stakeholders are highly satisfied with Access and Facilities in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao. Based on their knowledge, SDO Cabuyao personnel present themselves professionally to handle customer complaints and concerns to keep positive customer relations by allowing client to access each office for a certain transaction. SDO Cabuyao offers its clients drinking water and restrooms, which has turned into one of the services that is commendable. SDO Cabuyao is still improving and expanding its offerings, which included modern equipment, aesthetically pleasing lighting, computers, customer service counters and more.

The result was consistent with the recent study conducted by Marquez et al. (2019). It was stated that customer satisfaction served as the foundation for recognizing the issues experienced with the services provided by import processing firms, which served as a platform for the firms' future owners. Every single employee must be aware of how to manage client concerns and complaints to maintain good customer relations. The function of objectives in having a very satisfied client was fascinating and useful in terms of customer satisfaction. Because a client only interacts with a firm through customer service, it was crucial to an organization. Customers were essential to a business. Customers were the cornerstone of every business; without customers using their products or services, there would be no revenue to support operations. Undoubtedly, Ilfana et al. (2022) study resulted that product quality affected customer satisfaction, product quality affected customer loyalty, customer satisfaction affected customer loyalty, and product quality affected customer loyalty mediated by customer satisfaction.

Table 2.4

Communication was Fully Satisfied (3.46) in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao as assessed by the internal and external stakeholders. All indicators were verbally interpreted as Fully Satisfied. Furthermore, the indicator “SDO Cabuyao personnel act keeping citizens and businesses informed in a language they can easily understand, as well as listening to their feedback” had the highest computed mean of **3.50**. Meanwhile, the indicator “SDO Cabuyao personnel actively listen to your needs and concerns” had the lowest computed mean of **3.43**.

It is concluded that both internal and external Stakeholders in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao are extremely satisfied with the level of communication provided by SDO Cabuyao personnel, who act to inform clients in a language that is easily understood while also soliciting their feedback. One of the most crucial requirements to survive, satisfy and meet the needs of the clients is effective communication. Clients find that SDO Cabuyao personnel are knowledgeable about the topics being discussed and can effectively communicate the intended message during the communication process.

Considering the data presented above, Islam et al. (2023) mentioned that every business overcome obstacles to survive in the competitive market where clients are seen as the lifeblood of any business. Thus, customer satisfaction was an essential responsibility for every business. Similarly, Jones and Brown (2019) mentioned that effective communication and transparency in service delivery processes play a crucial role in assuring customers. Clear and timely information regarding service procedures, pricing, and potential risks fosters trust and reduces uncertainty, thereby enhancing satisfaction levels.

Table 2.5

The Internal and External Stakeholders in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao were **Fully Satisfied** in terms of **Cost** (Mean = **3.43**). All indicators were verbally interpreted as Fully Satisfied. Furthermore, the indicator “Satisfaction with the timelines of the billing, billing process/es, preferred methods of payment period, value for money, acceptable range of costs, and qualitative information on the cost of each service” had the highest computed mean of 3.48. Meanwhile, the indicator “Cost of the service accurately reflects the level of professionalism, expertise, and attention to detail exhibited” had the lowest computed mean of 3.38. It can be concluded that both internal and external stakeholders in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao are very satisfied with the following aspects of the cost: value for money, acceptable range of costs, preferred methods of payment period, timely billing, and qualitative information on the cost of each service. Before using the service, SDO Cabuyao provides clear and open cost information to clients to minimize any potential disputes, itemizes breakdown of the costs involved, such as service fees, additional charges, or taxes are being presented beforehand to meet client expectation toward the service cost. To support the result, according to Kotler and Keller (2016, as cited in Albari, 2020), customer satisfaction was the degree of a person’s emotions after comparing the performance or results he felt with his expectations. Correspondingly, Zhou et al. (2019) stated that a firm fairly and effectively carried out manufacturing decision-making guidance proposed a way to assess customer satisfaction based on the fuzzy level kano-QDF model. As a result, the client obtained changed products in a timely and satisfactory manner.

Table 2.6

Integrity was **Fully Satisfied (3.44)** in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao as assessed by the internal and external stakeholders. All indicators were verbally interpreted as Fully Satisfied. Furthermore, the indicator “SDO Cabuyao personnel can perform their duties, product, and service knowledge, understand client needs, helpfulness, and good work relationships” had the highest computed mean of 3.47. Meanwhile, the indicator “Clients feel safe in their transactions with personnel at the counters” had the lowest computed mean of 3.40.

It can be concluded that both internal and external stakeholders in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao are highly satisfied in terms of Integrity because client see SDO

Cabuyao personnel can carry out their jobs, knowledgeable about products and services, able to understand the needs of their clients, helpful, and honest in their work relationship. The service quality is greatly executed because it has a big impact on client satisfaction. Having a friendly demeanor always helps to build and maintain enduring relationships with clients towards satisfaction. It is consistent with the findings of Khong et al. (2023), cited that to increase customer satisfaction and loyalty, manufacturing companies should focus more on developing and innovating services. Service that accompanied the product, strengthens communications, and maintains long-term relationships with customers. In today's competitive market, the quality of the accompanying services plays a decisive role in affirming the position of the products produced by the enterprise compared to similar products of the competitors. Likewise, Brown and Garcia (2021) stated that ethical behavior, including fairness, respect, and adherence to ethical standards, contributes to perceptions of integrity and trustworthiness. Customers appreciate service providers who prioritize ethical considerations in their decision-making processes and interactions, leading to increased satisfaction and loyalty.

Table 2.7

Assurance was Fully Satisfied (3.47) in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao as assessed by the internal and external stakeholders. All indicators were verbally interpreted as Fully Satisfied. Furthermore, the indicators “SDO Cabuyao personnel are knowledgeable of the service offered” and “Clients have a safe transaction with personnel” had the highest computed mean of 3.49. Meanwhile, the indicator “SDO Cabuyao keep records with confidentiality and accuracy” had the lowest computed mean of 3.45.

When it comes to assurance, it can be concluded that both internal and external stakeholders in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao are extremely satisfied because SDO Cabuyao personnel are knowledgeable of the service offered. They feel safe while doing transaction with the personnel in every way, being honest, fair, and trustworthy in each service while dealing with clients and businesses are those factors to build assurance that is one of the predictors of satisfaction. Similarly, Choi and Lee (2020) stated that efficient handling of service failures and prompt resolution of customer complaints were essential for maintaining assurance of satisfaction. Studies suggested that customers were often more satisfied when service providers acknowledged and rectified mistakes promptly, demonstrating their commitment to customer-centricity. Evidently, Patel and Williams (2020) claimed that explicit service guarantees and policies provide customers with assurance regarding the quality and reliability of the service. When service providers offer warranties, satisfaction guarantees, and clear refund policies, it reduces perceived risks and enhances satisfaction levels.

Table 3.1

This means that teaching, non-teaching personnel, and parents have the same perception about Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance, and Tangibility. Several researchers including Kefalas (2019) mentioned that service quality was an indicator of a

successful business. By recognizing the individual expectations of customers, the dimensions of service quality, and its relative importance for customers in each section of the hotel industry, hotel managers can take on the issue of improving service quality. The fact that the level of expertise and talent of the server is always directly correlated with the quality of service in the hospitality sector is a significant barrier to standardizing services. Furthermore, it is impossible to legitimately standardize experiences because they are always subjective and vary from person to person. Correspondingly, Danish (as cited in Dider, 2021) described service quality as the comparison function connecting customer expectations to the service delivered. In contrast, Sibai et al. (2021) claimed that responsiveness, empathy and tangibility dimensions of service quality had a negative gap, which means that the expected services did not meet the perceived services on the cited service quality dimensions.

Table 3.2

There was no significant difference between the responses of the two groups of respondents on the level of satisfaction in terms of Responsiveness, Reliability, Access and Facilities, Communication, Cost, Integrity, and Assurance as shown in Table 3.2. The generated computed probability values were **.519, .823, .825, .808, .082, .798 and .488** respectively which were greater than the level of significance of 0.05; thus, the null hypothesis was accepted. This means that teaching, non-teaching personnel, and parents have the same perception with regards to Responsiveness, Reliability, Access and Facilities, Communication, Cost, Integrity, and Assurance.

In like manner with the study of Sibai et al. (2021), they concluded that when overall satisfaction was measured, students expressed satisfaction to the college services. Year level was a predictor for all measures of student satisfaction, while GPA was identified as a negative predictor to student satisfaction in terms of faculty. Students' satisfaction in terms of faculty was best predicted by responsiveness, assurance, tangibility. Meanwhile, assurance was a predictor of students' satisfaction in terms of curriculum. Responsibility, responsiveness, and assurance, on the other hand, were predictors of students' satisfaction in terms of students' services and facilities. Finally, overall student satisfaction was predicted by responsiveness, assurance, and tangibility. For this reason, Jiang et al. (2020) mentioned that by creating an evaluation model of customer satisfaction, it calculated customer satisfaction in different service industries and identified factors that influence customer satisfaction most.

Table 4

There was a **significant relationship** between the level of service quality and the level of satisfaction. The *r* values ranging from **.298 to .448** were interpreted as with a **moderate positive correlation** as to correlate level of service quality and level of satisfaction. The computed probability values of .000 were lesser than the level of significant ($P < 0.05$); thus, the null hypothesis is rejected.

It can be concluded that the higher the service quality in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao, the higher the stakeholders' satisfaction.

Numerous researchers including Marnovita (2020, as cited in Wibowo, 2022) stated that service quality was a strategy used by businesses to continuously improve the processes, goods, and services they produced. Service quality dimensions or indicators included customer satisfaction levels, which are inversely correlated with service quality levels. Likewise, Mulyadi (2020) mentioned that customer satisfaction was influenced by service quality, if clients were satisfied with the quality of the service, then this will be able to raise the degree of customer satisfaction. Importantly, according to Twum et al. (2020), customer satisfaction was 100% observed by dimensions of service quality i.e. Tangibility, Responsiveness, Reliability, Assurance and Empathy, through that customer needs must be given an attention. Additionally, Tan et al. (2022) showed the result indicated that four service quality dimensions (tangibles, assurance, reliability, and empathy) have a significant effect on the customers' perceived service quality from the library. Empathy was the strongest predictor of customers' perceived service quality, followed by reliability, tangibles, and assurance. The study revealed that customers' perceived service quality from the library was a significant predictor of customer satisfaction. Stakeholders' satisfaction is an extremely important factor that has an impact on a company's overall performance. In the fiercely competitive world of today, offering high quality customer service is essential and the cornerstone of any prosperous business.

Table 5

By implementing this action plan, City Schools Division of Cabuyao can cultivate a more empathetic culture, leading to improved employee-stakeholder relationships, enhanced collaboration, and a positive impact on overall well-being. Enhancing service quality with a focus on empathy involves creating a customer-centric culture where stakeholders feel understood, valued, and supported. Below is an action plan for enhancing empathy in service delivery. **Project CARE** was proposed to emphasize the importance of cultivating authentic relationships through empathy in stakeholders' interactions. It included more strategies and activities to enhance the level of service quality focusing empathy that might produce a high level of stakeholders' satisfaction.

Conclusions

After presenting the summary of findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. That the City Schools Division of Cabuyao has established a highly effective and customer-centric service culture. Internal and external stakeholders strongly agree that SDO Cabuyao personnel consistently demonstrate reliability, responsiveness, empathy, assurance, and tangibility in their service delivery. The organization has successfully satisfied stakeholders from its inception, with personnel consistently delivering promised services quickly and simply, showing kindness, alertness, and providing individual

attention. Despite significant workloads, personnel remain accessible, promptly addressing inquiries and recognizing individual expectations. Confidentiality is well-maintained, and personnel are knowledgeable about procedures, minimizing confusion. Timely responses and necessary adjustments are priorities in every transaction. The physical environment, including tables, chairs, and clear signages, contributes to an enhanced customer experience, aligning with the overall goal of meeting and exceeding stakeholders' expectations.

2. That the City Schools Division of Cabuyao has achieved a remarkable level of satisfaction among internal and external stakeholders. The positive feedback emphasizes the personnel's eagerness to assist, commitment to fulfilling promises with minimal errors, and proactive engagement in delivering accurate information through stakeholder participation. Stakeholders appreciate the genuine care exhibited by SDO Cabuyao personnel in finding solutions to issues and fostering positive word-of-mouth. The professional handling of complaints, provision of commendable services like drinking water and restrooms, and effective communication in easily understandable language contribute to a positive client experience. Transparent cost information and the personnel's capability, knowledge, helpfulness, and honesty further strengthen stakeholder relationships. The overall satisfaction is evident in stakeholders feeling safe during transactions, emphasizing the importance of trust, fairness, and honesty as key factors in building assurance, a significant predictor of satisfaction.

3. That teaching, non-teaching personnel, and parents have the same perception with regard to reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and tangibility. They have different perceptions with regard to empathy. In addition, teaching, non-teaching personnel, and parents have the same perception with regard to responsiveness, reliability, access and facilities, communication, cost, integrity, and assurance.

4. That when the level of service quality increases, the stakeholders' satisfaction also increases. However, when the level of service quality decreases, the stakeholders' satisfaction also decreases.

5. That Project CARE is needed to incorporate initiatives and strategies emphasizing the importance of cultivating authentic relationships through empathy in stakeholders' interactions which will lead to higher level of stakeholders' satisfaction.

Recommendations

Based on the above conclusions, suggestions and recommendations are listed below:

1. To maintain high-quality service, City School Division of Cabuyao may provide or conduct a series of programs for all personnel in the service at least twice a year. These initiatives are intended to improve service delivery methods, enhance customer expectations, and expedite response and resolve customer issues. Everyone in the

service may have an equal opportunity to gain knowledge and understand the importance of the training especially when it comes to dealing with internal and external stakeholders.

2. City Schools Division of Cabuyao top management may include reinforcement motivation for employees to be more engaged and increase desires and passion toward their job. A motivating stimulus, such as incentives or praise, is presented to reinforce desired behaviors. This increases the likelihood that the personnel will act in this way going forward. Employee motivation increases the likelihood that they will perform well overall, which boosts output and enhances customer satisfaction.

3. The Top Management, together with the Monitoring and Evaluation Section (M&E), may focus more on providing immediate solutions and effective intervention when there is undesirable feedback coming from internal and external stakeholders to show empathy towards the clients. The City Schools Division of Cabuyao may offer helpdesk support once a week at the very least to address and discuss stakeholder concerns that could aid in an urgent resolution.

4. To keep high performance and satisfaction, the need to deliver standard and necessary information to each employee in different departments through meetings monthly is thought to be essential to their ability to understand the processes of each department to avoid confusion on the part of the clients when there is a transaction. Thus, SDO personnel will be capable of keeping informed and spreading awareness on the processes and regulations among different units so that become a reliable source at the same time. Conducting meetings will also be very beneficial in disseminating information about the services being offered.

5. City Schools Division of Cabuyao may utilize Project CARE to enhance and further develop the satisfaction of its internal and external stakeholders, as this is the most important and reflection of service quality, which has a big impact on the divisions' image and reputation.

6. Although, there are lots of literature on the subject, more research on service quality, as well as how to maintain client satisfaction, may be conducted. To gain a deeper understanding of the client's experience of the service, it is also advised that future research use a qualitative strategy rather than a quantitative approach. As a result of this initiative, the City Schools Division of Cabuyao will have a great chance to perform all necessary analysis regarding the quality of its services.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Ethical consideration is one of the most important aspects of the research. This research had the respondents' informed consent before the trial. The research survey respondents' dignity was not violated in any way and was given top attention. Finally,

during the process, consideration was given to maintaining the privacy and security of the information obtained.

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